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Entangled particles model

Here we consider a mathematical model of such particles that instantly communicate some information to each other without spending energy on receiving and transmitting this information. It is proved that particles capable of emitting and receiving radiation, as well as having a common reception and transmission frequency, are entangled, i.e. can exchange instant messages, regardless of the distance between them and without wasting energy. The author came up with the idea of developing such a model after the appearance of the works of V.P. Zaitsev, in which the existence of solar rays propagating at infinite speed was experimentally proven.

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1. Introduction

Despite the prevalence of the term “entangled particles,” there is no strict definition of this concept. Therefore, first of all, let's say what we intend to model. We will consider a model of such particles that instantly communicate some information to each other without spending energy on receiving and transmitting this information.

2. Cylindrical wave

Further we will use the SI system, cylindrical coordinates r, φ, z, t and the following notation:

$$c_0 = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (1)$$

$$s_i = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (2)$$

where α, χ, ω are some constants, the physical meaning of which is explained in [3, Chapter 1]. It was proven there that one of the solutions to Maxwell's system of equations is a strictly cylindrical wave, in which there are 4 intensities, the vectors of which are directed along the radius (radial) and along the circle (circumferential):

$$H_{r.} = h_r(r)c_0, \quad (3)$$

$$H_{\varphi.} = h_{\varphi}(r)s_i, \quad (4)$$

$$E_{r.} = e_r(r)s_i, \quad (5)$$

$$E_{\varphi.} = e_{\varphi}(r)c_0, \quad (6)$$

where E_r, E_{φ} are electrical intensities, H_r, H_{φ} are magnetic intensities, $h(r), e(r)$ are functions of coordinate r the following form

$$e_r = e_{\varphi} = \frac{A}{2} r^{\alpha-1}, \quad (6)$$

$$h_{\varphi}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r(r), \quad (7)$$

$$h_r(r) = -h_{\varphi}(r), \quad (8)$$

$$\chi = \omega\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (9)$$

where A is a certain constant and ε, μ are the absolute values of electrical and magnetic permeability.

Electromagnetic energy density in this wave

$$W(r) = \varepsilon e_r^2 \quad (10)$$

constant in time and the same at all points of a cylinder of a given radius.

The flow of electromagnetic energy in this wave is directed only along the axis of the cylinder; there is no radial radiation. The density of this flow

$$S_z(r) = e_r h_{\varphi} = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2 \quad (11)$$

The speed of this flow

$$v = 1/\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}. \quad (12)$$

Note that the speed of light in vacuum

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\varepsilon_0\mu_0}, \quad (13)$$

where ε_0, μ_0 are the values ε, μ in vacuum.

A cylindrical wave also rotates around its axis with angular velocity

$$\omega_{\varphi} = \frac{\omega}{\alpha}. \quad (14)$$

and has rotational energy with density

$$Q(r) = W(r) \left(\frac{\omega r}{ac}\right)^2, \quad (15)$$

which is shown in [4].

In Fig. 1 in the first window at the top shows a spiral - the geometric locus of points of one value of the total vector $\vec{E}_{r\varphi} = \vec{E}_r + \vec{E}_\varphi$. The second window from the top shows the same spiral for the case when the energy flow is directed in the opposite direction. In the lower window, both spirals are combined in one spatial cylinder. The same spirals exist for the total vector $\vec{H}_{r\varphi} = \vec{H}_r + \vec{H}_\varphi$. Spiral pitch

$$\Lambda = \frac{2\pi\alpha}{\chi} r. \tag{16}$$

Oppositely directed energy flows can exist in one physical cylinder.

Rice. 1.

3. Design

In Fig. 1 shows the end points A and B of the helices. Let us place at these points some structures called “emitter-receiver” - ER. The ER emits an electromagnetic wave and receives the electromagnetic wave emitted by the opposite ER. The emitted and received waves carry the same energy flow. Therefore, this design does not consume energy to transmit the energy flow. Energy is spent by the ER on analyzing the received flow and creating an opposite flow with the same flow value. The analysis may consist of determining the magnitude of the flow. The

amount of the received stream may be information for the receiver, based on which it can change the amount of the sent stream or change this value in accordance with its internal state (or perhaps in accordance with the content of information received over time. In this way it can be coordinated behavior of the pair ER is organized.

We got, one might say, a entangled pair of ERs. It is entangled with the help of a cylindrical wave, which can be arbitrarily extended and does not lose energy along the way. A pair of entangled ERs does not waste energy transmitting and receiving information.

But, compared to entangled particles, this pair has a significant drawback - a delay in the response to reception, which is caused by the finite speed of transmission of the energy flow.

4. Zaitsev's experiments with elementary particles bison

Zaitsev V.P. proved experimentally and showed in a series of articles in the journal DNA (see, in particular, [1, 2]) that there are solar rays that travel at a speed much lower and much higher than the speed of light. Among the many surprising phenomena obtained in this fundamental discovery, we will be interested in the fact that there are 17 rays, the velocities of which are determined as follows. Consider the scale of numbers n these rays:

$$n = [-7, -6, \dots, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots, 8, 9]. \quad (1)$$

Spread speed n -ray

$$v_n = \begin{cases} c \cdot F_1 \frac{1}{7-n}, & \text{if } n < 0, \\ c, & \text{if } n = 0, \\ c \cdot F_2 \frac{1}{9-n}, & \text{if } n > 0, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where F_1, F_2 are some constants. The most striking thing about this formula is that

$$v_9 = \infty. \quad (3)$$

Zaitsev explains this discovery by the existence of previously unknown particles - bisons, which are emitted not only by the photosphere of the Sun, but also by other - terrestrial sources of radiation. The existence of particles - carriers of radiation is based on the universally recognized fact of the existence of photons - carriers of electromagnetic radiation. However, the author also has the opposite opinion - the statement that the electron is a physical illusion, and all the properties of the photon (because of which it appeared in science) can be explained by the fact that the electromagnetic wave rotates [4].

Remaining within the framework of classical electrodynamics, we will further describe electromagnetic waves with a propagation speed different from the speed of light, we will use formulas to determine this speed, energy densities and energy flow (2.12, 2.10, 2.11):

$$v = 1/\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (1)$$

$$W(r) = \varepsilon e_r^2, \quad (2)$$

$$S(r) = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2. \quad (3)$$

Let us also write down Umov's formula:

$$S(r) = v \cdot W(r). \quad (4)$$

For the existence of velocities, it is necessary to recognize that they propagate in space with permeabilities μ, ε , other than ε_0, μ_0 . We will call such a space

$\mu\varepsilon$ -space,

and the quantity $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon)$ will be called the permeability of such space. From Zaitsev's experiments and formulas (1-3) it follows:

1. several $\mu\varepsilon$ -spaces can exist in one physical space;
2. any emitter emits a "fan" of rays spreading in $17 \mu\varepsilon$ -spaces;
3. as permeability $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon)$ decreases, wave speed increases;
4. substance X is in its $\varepsilon_x \mu_x$ -space;
5. a wave, having collided with substance X, passes into its $\varepsilon_x \mu_x$ -space and transfers energy to the substance, the density of which is determined in accordance with formulas (4, 1):

$$W = \frac{S}{v_x} = S \sqrt{\varepsilon_x \mu_x} \quad (5)$$

no matter from which space the wave came;

6. in $\mu\varepsilon$ -space with zero quantity $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon) = 0$ speed is infinite – see (1); We will call such a space with zero permeability impenetrable; it is paradoxical that it is precisely impenetrable space that the ray penetrates with infinite speed;
7. the energy density of a beam penetrating at an infinite speed through an impenetrable space is zero, because in it $\varepsilon_0 = 0$ - see (2);
8. The energy flux density in such a beam can be any because in it $\varepsilon_0 = 0, \mu_0 = 0$ - see - see formulas (3, 4):

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2 \equiv \sqrt{0} - \text{any quantity}, \quad (6)$$

$$S = v \cdot W = \infty \cdot 0 - \text{any quantity}. \quad (7)$$

5. Entangled particles

From the above it follows that any emitter radiates to the whole world, informing the whole world about its existence. Only this radiation has very low power. In addition, not every receiver is tuned to all frequencies. Taking this into account and based on the proposed design, it can be argued that

particles capable of emitting and receiving radiation, and also having a common frequency of reception and transmission, are entangled, i.e. can exchange instant messages, regardless of the distance between them and without wasting energy.

Obviously, many particles can be part of a “community of particles entangled at a certain frequency.”

References

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